

A Knowledge Graph-Based Conversational Agent for Analyzing User Interactions

Christos Bouas¹[0009-0002-8809-3303], Maria Papoutsoglou¹[0000-0003-0658-5065],
Alexandros Tassios¹[0009-0009-7922-339X], Stergios Tegos¹[0009-0000-3857-1552],
Konstantinos Manousaridis¹[0009-0003-0557-2542], Maria
Kaltsa^{2,3}[0000-0002-2422-7889], Thanassis Mavropoulos³[0000-0002-7326-5910],
Stefanos Vrochidis³[0000-0002-2505-9178], and Georgios
Meditskos¹[0000-0003-4242-5245]

¹ School of Informatics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

² Department of Theoretical & Applied Linguistics, School of English, Aristotle
University of Thessaloniki, Greece

³ Information Technologies Institute, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas,
Greece

Abstract. This paper discusses ongoing work in the SALLY research project, which aims to help migrants in Greece integrate using conversational agent technology. The main users of SALLY are Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in Greece, who can interact with the agent to get information on topics like legal processes, available services, and other important matters. To improve the chatbot’s performance, it was important to better understand how users interact with SALLY. To support this goal, we developed a secondary chatbot designed to help SALLY administrators analyze user interactions. This chatbot was trained using real conversations between users and SALLY and is intended for administrator use only. User conversations within SALLY are stored along with key details in knowledge graphs. These details include important parts of the conversations, such as mentioned entities, relationships, and private concepts. The stored information is then used to train the secondary chatbot, allowing administrators to gain useful insights from user interactions.

Keywords: Knowledge Graphs · Large Language Models · Chatbot · Migrant Integration.

1 Introduction

The use of Large Language Models (LLMs) is abundant, with them finding a place in many projects and services across different domains [13]. Our research project, SALLY, aims to use them for migrant integration in Greece. SALLY research project aims to assist Third Country Nationals (TCNs) residing in Greece by developing a conversational agent. Our chatbot (also called “SALLY”) utilizes several technologies, merging statistical-based LLMs with structured,

formalized knowledge in the form of Knowledge Graphs. It also uses Dialogue Management [2], Information Retrieval [5], and Sentiment Analysis [12]. Users can interact with SALLY in English and Greek. A technical overview of the SALLY chatbot is presented in [11].

In the context of enhancing our agent’s performance, we wanted to gain further insights into how users interact with SALLY and explore interaction patterns. We have previously created a knowledge extraction system, which takes user-agent conversations as input and outputs knowledge graphs containing the conversation along with metadata such as the user’s dialogue act, sentiment, as well as any entities, relations, concepts, etc. found in the user utterances. These graphs form the SALLY knowledge graph, which stores all conversations.

In this paper we describe a complementary chatbot which will assist administrators of the SALLY platform. Since the SALLY knowledge graph will get larger as more users chat with SALLY, it will be harder to study the graph directly. This is the motivation behind the complementary chatbot presented here: to serve as a tool for SALLY administrators so that they can study interaction patterns more effectively. This chatbot was trained on conversation users had with SALLY. Our approach involves the use of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), fine-tuned for drawing knowledge from a knowledge graph.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents related work in the area. Section 3 describes the chatbot for administrators, showing examples of the training knowledge graph data and detailing the architecture of the system. Section 4 shows examples of the system in use, showing interactions between administrators and the chatbot as well as discussing potential insights to be gained from using the chatbot. Section 5 concludes this paper and suggests directions for future research.

2 Related work

Analysis of chatbot conversations has been the topic of many research works. For example, Akhtar et al. [1] analyze conversations between a chatbot and a telecommunications company’s customers to identify user topics and user satisfaction. To achieve this they employ text mining techniques. In a similar domain, Kvale et al. [9] analyze chatbot responses and try to identify the cases where the chatbot successfully replied to the questions. The same purpose had Li et al. [10] when analyzing a large dataset of chatbot responses, identifying that in several cases these were not satisfactory. Moreover, Folstad and Taylor [3] propose a framework for qualitative analysis of chatbots. Jalota et al [7] perform an ex-post-facto analysis over the logs of knowledge base-driven dialogue systems.

Unlike previous approaches that focus on post-hoc analysis using traditional log inspection or text mining techniques, our system allows administrators to query user interaction data through a conversational agent powered by a knowledge graph. This enables structured access to both conversational content and metadata (e.g., dialogue acts, topics, fluency) in a way that is both interpretable and extensible.

3 Description of the system

3.1 Data

Conversations of users with SALLY serve as the training data for our complementary chatbot. Specifically, the data is in the form of a knowledge graph, the SALLY knowledge graph, containing all the conversations along with metadata. Table 1 describes the data we store for each user utterance of a conversation, which includes the metadata we extract from them. We extract this metadata using a knowledge extraction tool we created for this purpose.

To support the SALLY knowledge graph, we have created an OWL ontology in order to formally define how the graph should be structured. The ontology serves as scaffolding for the generation of the SALLY knowledge graph, which must follow the definitions described in the ontology.

Below we list the classes we included in our ontology. The superclass for all classes is owl:Thing, no classes have any subclasses.

- **Session**: a conversation between some user and the chatbot.
- **Message**: an utterance (user utterances only).
- **Entity**: people, places, events, etc.
- **Relation**: triples of the form (subject, relation type, object). They connect entities.
- **Concept**: subsumes the definition of an entity, but is broader than it.
- **Private Concept**: concepts that are sensitive in nature.

To ensure user privacy, all input data in our system is anonymized before storage. Our processing pipeline identifies and obfuscates personally identifiable information, such as names and nationalities, which are tagged as *Private Concepts* in our ontology. Furthermore, the project follows established ethical guidelines and best practices for data handling and storage, including compliance with informed consent procedures and secure data management.

The knowledge extraction tool takes as input a conversation chatlog containing only the user utterances. Then, it processes utterances one at a time, until it has processed them all. To process an utterance, it translates it to English using the Google Translator from the Deep Translator package. Afterwards, it needs to extract data for all of the types mentioned in Table 1, bar the text as it is already provided. The table describes the data we want to store for each user utterance of a conversation, including the metadata we want to extract from them.

We use a combination of existing tools, as well as custom prompts to an LLM to extract the data. The *Language* of an utterance is identified using the Langdetect package. *Entities* are extracted the named entity recognition module of spaCy [6] with the `en_core_web_sm` model. Additionally, *Entities* are linked to DBpedia utilizing the DBpedia Spotlight API. *Concepts* are extracted using the already discovered *Entities* as well as extracted key phrases. *Concepts* that do refer to people or places form the set of *Private Concepts*. The rest of the

Table 1. The data we store in our graph for each user utterance.

Data	Description
Text	A short description of what the text is about.
Topic	The topic of the utterance.
Dialogue act	The aim of the user.
Sentiment	Description of the sentiment expressed by the user.
Language	The language the utterance is in.
Fluency	The fluency level of the utterance.
Concepts	Concepts are specific terms found in the text. These may include name, age, profession and more.
Private Concepts	Concepts that are private or sensitive information, such as names and nationalities.
Entities	Entities found in the text, such as people and countries.
Relations	Relations between the entities. These can be nationalities, familial relationships, and more. Relations are represented by triples (subject, type of relation, object).

types are extracting using an LLM, specifically Llama 3.1 8B [4], prompting it appropriately for each type.

After extracting the metadata we create a knowledge graph for each conversation, which we merge with the SALLY knowledge graph. We populate the conversation’s graph with the extracted elements right after extracting them. For simpler extracted types, namely *Topic*, *Dialogue act*, *Sentiment*, *Language*, and *Fluency*, we use data properties, storing them as strings. For more complex types, namely *Concept*, *Private Concept*, *Entity*, and *Relation*, we use individuals from these classes along with object properties. These types are comprised of lists of items, links, or, in the case of relations, subjects and objects.

Figure 1 shows the utterances of a test conversation. The conversation session (beige) is comprised of three user messages (yellow). We have expanded some relationships for the first message. The user utterance for this message was "*Hi, I am Ahmed. I used to work as a civil engineer in Syria. I came to Greece with my wife and our two kids. I want to find a job here, any job.*" Our tool identified some entities in this text (magenta) and found links to DBpedia for them. It also identified relations (blue), as well as concepts and private concepts (same as the entities - relationships not depicted). Examples of relations identified by the tool include (Ahmed, workedIn, Syria) and (Ahmed, locatedIn, Greece).

3.2 System architecture

The complementary chatbot for SALLY administrators was built using Python, while Neo4j is used as a database to store and retrieve textual knowledge. The chatbot’s architecture is LLM-agnostic—any LLM can be used to drive its conversations as well as any embeddings service.

¹ <https://neo4j.com/product/bloom/>

Fig. 1. Visualization of a part of a conversation graph using Neo4j Bloom. ¹

Figure 2 presents the architecture of the complementary chatbot. Each conversation with SALLY (i.e. the main conversational agent) is fed to our knowledge extraction system which extracts useful metadata from the user utterances of the conversation. This is then stored into the SALLY knowledge graph. The knowledge base of the complementary chatbot is built using the SALLY knowledge graph, out of which we create “chunk” nodes, embedded sentences generated from triples (subject, predicate, object) in the knowledge graph we construct a natural language sentence, subject predicate object, and curate it by removing namespaces and paraphrasing it slightly according to the predicate. For example, the triple (sally:Ahmed, sally:entityType, ‘PERSON’) where Ahmed is an Entity, becomes the sentence Entity Ahmed is a person. Each sentence is then embedded using the selected embeddings service.

To assist project administrators in reviewing and managing conversations, we developed a web-based administrator platform. This interface provides an overview of all user-system interactions, displaying information such as timestamps, conversation IDs, the initial user message, number of dialogue turns, average response length, and response time. The platform allows administrators to monitor usage and identify issues, and it supports filtering and sorting across all available fields. Figure 3 shows a screenshot of this interface. Currently, the knowledge extraction tool is used as a command-line interface (CLI) application, but integration into the administrator platform is planned for future development to streamline the workflow for administrators.

Administrator queries are transformed into an embedding and then passed to the retrieval mechanism which performs a cosine similarity search against the indexed chunk embeddings of the knowledge base and returns the most relevant

Fig. 2. The architecture of the chatbot. Created using diagrams.net.²

TIMESTAMP	ID	EMAIL	CONVERSATION	NO OF TURNS (WORDS)	AVG. RESPONSE LENGTH	AVG RESPONSE TIME (MS)
2025-05-04 15:50:02	zmvfvhjvnasp90fn7xbbdg8m		Hi, I want to learn more about the temporary housing facilities.	5	147 characters	2.87 ms
2025-05-04 15:47:42	z3d7lesr683fyz45ggqqgw7m		Will I receive treatment if I go to a hospital?	5	248 characters	2.68 ms

Fig. 3. The SALLY administrator platform.

matches. These matches are inserted into a predefined prompt template, which constrains the language model to generate responses based on retrieved context.

As users chat with SALLY, new conversations are added to the SALLY knowledge graph. The knowledge base of the complementary chatbot needs to continuously evolve with new information, efficiently adding new embeddings while minimizing redundant computations. For each new conversation we construct a sentence out of its knowledge graph, as described before, and then create a chunk with a vector representation for it and add it to the knowledge base.

4 Examples

In this section, we present some examples of our chatbot in use during test interactions. As mentioned previously the chatbot is LLM-agnostic. For this demonstration we have used Mistral’s 7B model [8] and Cohere’s embeddings.

² <https://app.diagrams.net/>

Fig. 4. Part of the graph of the test conversations out of which the chatbot’s knowledge base was built. Visualization using Bloom.

The goal of these interactions is to study the responses of the system to typical queries asked by administrators. Our aim with this work is for SALLY administrators to use this complementary chatbot to extract useful conclusions from user conversations with SALLY and study interaction patterns.

The knowledge base we use for these examples is a toy one and not the full one which is based on the SALLY knowledge graph of real user conversations. The knowledge base was generated from a graph of three test conversation sessions. The first session is about temporary housing facilities for migrants in Greece. The second session is about someone whose asylum application was rejected and who wants to learn about their options. Finally, the third session is about Ahmed, a Syrian civil engineer who came to Greece with his family and who wants to find a job.

Figure 4 shows a part of the knowledge graph which was used to build the knowledge base of the chatbot for these examples.

Following are two scenarios illustrating the capabilities of the system.

4.1 Scenario 1

In this usage scenario, the administrator wants to know about the metadata in some user utterance. We expect this to be a common query type, as SALLY administrators will ask about specific user utterances as they utilize the chatbot to extract knowledge about a user-SALLY conversation. These queries include asking for general information about the utterance, such the type of sentiment found, as well as asking more complex questions about the metadata. Following are two such queries accompanied by the responses given by our complementary chatbot. The first query asks about the entities found in a user utterance, specifically the one shown in Figure 1. The chatbot correctly identifies the entities “Ahmed”, “two”, and “Syria”. The second query asks about the nation Ahmed is from. The system responds with the correct answer, “Syria”.

Query 1 What entities are found in `sally3_message1`?

Response

The entities found in `sally3_message1` are Ahmed, two, and Syria.

Query 2 Where is Ahmed from?

Response

Ahmed is from Syria.

4.2 Scenario 2

In this usage scenario, the administrator wants to know general information about the graph. We also expect this to be a common query type, as it provides a user-friendly front through which administrators will be able to extract knowledge about the graph using natural language. These queries would otherwise need to be expressed in some query language (e.g. Neo4j Cypher). SALLY Administrators will be able to quickly and reliably get answers about macro-scale topics like the number of sessions in the knowledge base. Following are three example queries accompanied by the responses of our chatbot. The first query asks whether any sessions begin with just a greeting, to which the chatbot correctly responds that no such sessions exist. The second query inquires how many conversations end with a thank you; the chatbot identifies two such cases. Finally, the third query asks about the most common dialogue act across all sessions, and the chatbot identifies “request information” as the most frequent.

Query 1 Are there any sessions that begin with just a greeting?

Response

No, there are no sessions that begin with just a greeting.

Query 2 How many conversations end with a thank you?

Response

Two conversations end with a thank you.

Query 3 What is the most common dialogue act across all sessions?

Response

The most common dialogue act across all sessions is request information.

5 Discussion & Conclusion

In this paper we introduced a complementary chatbot for administrators of our research project, SALLY. The chatbot is trained on user conversations with SALLY’s main chatbot and utilizes RAG using a knowledge graph to answer questions about these conversations. We have given an overview of the knowledge graph structure the conversations are stored in, also providing a description of the metadata. Furthermore, we have discussed the architecture of our conversational agent and the services we used to build it. Additionally, we have included examples of the complementary chatbot in use, showing how our system can be used to gain insights into user interaction patterns.

This complementary chatbot allows us to perform efficient analysis on the conversation data and gain insights on user interaction patterns. This, ultimately, helps us improve the SALLY chatbot down the line, by finding potential areas of improvement.

Despite our efforts, several challenges remain. Knowledge graph metadata accuracy depends on our underlying knowledge extraction tool, which in turn uses several other tools for extracting metadata. Moreover, our chatbot could be improved through better embedding creation and handling hallucinations. Future enhancements will focus on refining the accuracy of the knowledge extraction tool and better fine-tuning our complementary chatbot.

Beyond the context of SALLY, similar systems could support administrators in other domains such as healthcare or education, where understanding user interaction patterns is equally valuable. Adapting our approach to new domains would primarily require adjusting the knowledge graph schema to accommodate domain-specific interactions and terminology.

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